

Leadership of Female Madrasa Heads in Realizing a Superior Madrasa

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ABSTRACT

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This research was aimed to describe of type, behavior and leadership tactics of female madrasa heads in realizing the institution image as a superior madrasa which the public still in doubt. This research is qualitative which design was multi case study. The data was collected through in-depth interview, observation, and documentation method. The data then was analyzed using interactive model (display, condensation, and verification) data. The result showed: 1) The leadership type of female madrasah heads is a combination of visionary, democratic, innovator, conservator, advocate, administrative, semi-militaristic and paternalistic; 2) Leadership behavior is related to tasks, relationships with subordinates and the level of maturity between the leader and the task, subordinates and the level of maturity of subordinates which reflects the presence of contingent reward, management by-exception-active, idealized influence/attribution, idealized influence/behaviors, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, individualized considering, telling, selling, participating and delegating; 3) Leadership tactics are carried out using an approach of will, discipline, commitment, self-confidence, development of superior academic and extracurricular programs, development of social and environmental programs as well as supervision of institutions, teachers and students to excel. The research results strengthen Golleman's visionary leadership type concept that visionary leadership is oriented towards shared dreams by achieving a determined vision, as well as strengthening Bass & Avolio's concept of leadership behavior that leadership behavior is closely related to task dimensions, relationship patterns and subordinate maturity.

KEYWORDS:

leadership, female, superior, madrasa

1. INTRODUCTION

Quality education can be achieved when all educational components support such as input, process and output, which are well organized, the school principal as the party directly related to the implementation of educational programs in schools. As a policy maker, the principal must be able to function their role optimally and to lead the school wisely and directly in achieving maximum goals, and to improve the quality of education (Munir 2008, 6).

Institutions educational Leaders are people who carry out educational leadership with responsibility of influencing, inviting, organizing, coordinating personnel or employees towards the implementation and improvement the quality of education and teaching so that it can run as expected (Syafaruddin 2005, 161).

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School principals are required to have a commitment to improve quality in their main function, therefore it must be focused on the quality of learning and all other staff who support it (Syafaruddin 2005, 52). The principal task is not only ordering and instructing his subordinates, but they have to be responsible for educational management which is directly related to the learning process in the school as stated in article 12 paragraph 1 PP 28 of 1990, that the principal is responsible for the implementation of educational activities, administration schools, development of other educational personnel, and utilization and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure (Mulyasa 2005, 24–25).

Leadership can be carried out by all people regardless of gender because awareness of the increase in women's resources is increasingly evident, which is indicated by the increasing the number of women pursuing higher education (Nasarudin 2001, 3). However, in social and cultural reality, there is still a view based on biological and psychological differences between men and women that in general the structure and shape of women's bodies look soft

and melodious, while men tend to have strong, hard, brave characters and big voices, women and men have different brain weights, differences in nervous and blood systems which influence differences in their respective characters (Lily 1999, 68).

Men relate to the masculine dimension, so they are considered more competent, achievement oriented, strong, independent, active and self-confident. Meanwhile, women are related to the feminine dimension, considered incompetent, weak, dependent and not confident (Christina & Novianto 2004, 163). Meanwhile, to be a successful leader needs traits that are in the masculine dimension, which are usually found in men. Leadership is also synonymous with hard work, so leadership positions are often considered only suitable for men.

The results of research by Jirasinghe and Lyons, female school principals describe themselves as more sociable, democratic, caring, artistic, well-behaved, careful, thorough, having feeling, and careful (Tony & Marianne 2006, 101). The dominant leadership style used by men is instructional leadership, while women use democratic leadership. Besides, women's leadership is more successful than men's leadership because elementary schools whose quality of education is categorized as good, favorite, and have many students are led by women (Afrizal 2011). Most female principals have a leadership style that is motivated by good relationships with their subordinates (Setiowati & Okasiana 2010). Women's leadership uses Fiedler's contingency leadership model; there is trust between the leader and its members, a good leader's personality, the leader's firmness and loyalty, members' respect for the leader and a clear work structure.

Shoya Zichy's in Tilaar stated that there are eight types of female leadership, namely: trustee type, conservator, tactician, realistic, strategic, innovator, mentor, and the advocate type (Tilaar & Widarto 2003). In line with this research, Zaniyati et al said that the presence of women as heads of madrasas in Jombang showed exemplary, tenacity, firmness, professionalism and competence, women can produce extraordinary achievements. In approximately a year and a half they were able to change a madrasah that was "in decline" into a madrasah that are able to compete with others. The efforts made by female madrasa heads can dispel the doubts about women are less capable of leading. For this reason, it is time for the Central Ministry of Religion to implement gender mainstreaming with a 30% quota for the government in the form of clear rules or guidelines, so it can be implemented in the regional Ministry of Religion (Zaniyati & Salaman 2011).

This research was conducted at 2 madrasas in Jombang (MTs al Hikam and MTsN 16 Jombang), these two madrasas have succeeded in showing a significant increase in institutional quality and demonstrated their existence as favorite secondary schools with various achievements at both

local and national levels even though both are located in suburban areas of Jombang.

This research used a qualitative approach, the data collection used in-depth interviews, observation and documentation (Bodgan & Biklen 2007), the data was then analyzed using interactive models, namely display data, condensation, and verification (Miles, Huberman, & Saldana 2020, 380).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Leadership

Leadership is the characteristic of a leader in assuming formal moral and legal responsibility for all implementation of authority has been delegated to the people he leads (Hikmat 2009, 149). Leadership effectiveness is influenced by several factors including: a) personality, past experiences and leader expectations, b) expectations and superiors' behavior, c) characteristics of expectations and subordinates' behavior, d) task needs, e) climate and its policy and f) expectations and colleagues s' behavior (Fatah 2004, 98). The attitude, character and effectiveness of a leader can be seen from the perspective of consideration and initiation structure, where a leader positions himself towards his subordinates as individuals, as well as positions himself as a leader for the people he leads (Wahjosumidjo 2010, 24–26).

According to (Kartono 2008), there are several types of leadership as follows:

The charismatic leadership type is a leader who has extraordinary energy, charm and character to influence other people, so that he has a very large number of followers and bodyguards can be trusted. Paternalistic leadership is more identified with fatherly leadership with the following characteristics:(1) they consider their subordinates as humans who are not/immature, or their own children who need to be developed, (2) they are overly protective, (3) they rarely give subordinates opportunity to make their own decisions, (4) they almost never give opportunities to subordinates to take the initiative, (5) they almost never give followers or subordinates the opportunity to develop their own imagination and creativity, (6) they always act omniscient and Omni right. This type of militaristic leadership is very similar to the authoritarian leadership. The characteristics of the militaristic type of leadership are (1) using more orders/command systems, harsh and very authoritarian, rigid, and often lacking intact, (2) requiring absolute obedience from subordinates, (3) really liking formalities and ceremonies ritual and excessive signs of greatness, (4) demanding strict and rigid discipline from his subordinates, (5) they do not want advice, suggestions, and criticism from his subordinates, (6) the communication only takes place in one direction.

Autocratic leadership has such characteristics, as (1) basing itself on absolute power and coercion must be obeyed, (2) the leader always acts as a single player, (3) ambitious to

dominate the situation, (4) all orders and policy are always determined by himself, (5) subordinates are never given detailed information about plans and actions that will be carried out, (6) all praise and criticism of subordinates is given based on personal considerations, (7) exclusivism, (8) willing to absolute power, (9) his attitudes and principles are very conservative, old-fashioned, strict and rigid, (10) His goodness is based on the subordinate's obedience (Kartono 2008, 72).

According to (Hidayat 2012, 84), *laissez faire* leaderships only function as a symbol, they have no technical skills, authority, and they cannot control subordinates, unable to carry out work coordination, create a cooperative work atmosphere. Their positions as leaders are usually obtained by bribery, kickbacks or due to a system of nepotism, meanwhile democratic leadership lies in the active participation of each group, it respects the potential of each individual and listens to advice and suggestions from subordinates. Visionary leadership is the leader's ability to create, formulate, communicate, socialize, transform, and implementing ideal thoughts that originate from him or as result of social interactions between organizational members and stakeholders which are believed to be the organization's goals that must be achieved through the commitment of all personnel (Komariah 2004, 82).

Leadership behavior is a leadership style in implementing leadership functions and strategies oriented on the task and subordinate. There are at least three dimensions: a) task behavior which refers to giving instructions by the leader to subordinates including certain explanations, something must be done, time, and the way to do it, as well as monitoring them closely; b) relationship behavior, refers to how invitations are conveyed by leaders through two-way communication which includes listening and involving subordinates in problem solving; c) maturity, refers to the ability and willingness of subordinates to take responsibility for carrying out the tasks assigned to them (Efendi 2015, 158–59). It is in line with statement of effective people such as being proactive, starting with the end in mind, and accustomed to putting the main things first, renewing oneself continuously/self-renewal (Coverly 1989, 168).

Referring to the concept developed by Avolio as quoted by Sahertian, task-oriented leadership is measured through three indicators; namely (1) contingent reward is behavior that always recognizes employee achievements and explains expectations; (2) management by-exception-active is the behavior of a leader who will take immediate action to correct problems and point out errors occurred; and (3) management by exception-passive is the behavior of a leader who will wait until the problem becomes chronic or serious before making corrections (Sahertian & Matahero 2010). According to (Blanchard & Hersey 2013, 80) there are five indicators to measure leadership behavior related to the maturity of subordinates, such as; a) informing/telling; b)

peddling/selling; c) involving/participating; d) delegating or low assignment.

Yukl developed the influence behavior questionnaire (IBQ) method which formulates nine strategies and techniques for influencing other people.

- a. Rational Persuasion: a strategy to convince other people by using logical and rational arguments.
- b. Inspiration Appeals Tactics: a tactic by asking for ideas or proposals to arouse enthusiasm and enthusiasm from the target person.
- c. Consultation tactics: the strategy of asking the target person to actively participate in the activities on the agenda.
- d. Ingratiation tactics: tactics to please the person, before making the actual request.
- e. Personal appeals tactics: a strategy to influence the target person on the basis of friendship, friendship or other personal matters.
- f. Exchange tactics: a strategy to utilize the exchange of understanding regarding like, pleasures, hobbies, etc. between us and the target person.
- g. Coalition tactics: the strategy of forming a coalition and asking for help from other parties to influence the target person.
- h. Pressure tactics: the strategy of influencing the target person with pressure warnings or threats.
- i. Legitimizing tactics: tactics that use authority and position to influence the target person (Yukl 1998, 525).

The presence of women in public spaces can be seen from three aspects, namely, (1) descriptive, substantive and transformative presence (Philips 1998, 12). Descriptive presence is women's involvement in public spaces referring to women's physical presence in political, economic and social institutions; their presence is a symbol of women being present (complementary) in the institution according to quota provisions. Substantive presence states that women's involvement refers to the substantive content of how far individuals influence political decisions. While transformative presence refers to the impact of a person's participation in political institutions on themselves and their group (Zaniyati & Salaman 2011, 75).

The Prophet's leadership principles can be summarized as follows:

- a. Shidiq (honest). Words that match actions can generate respect and trust from other people.
- b. Trustworthy. Trust can be interpreted as actually conveying something that he is assigned to convey.
- c. Tabligh is transmitter of treatises or messages to the people.
- d. Fathonah, means having good external and leadership skills.
- e. Charismatic is characterized by a perfect figure, perfect soul, noble character and honorable nature.

- f. Strong self-confidence. If you are determined to do something that is considered a matter of honor and pride, then nothing can dampen that determination and you will even be brave enough to face danger for the sake of it.
- g. High commitment. It provides a strong influence in leadership. Ready to carry a heavy burden on his shoulders without complaining in carrying out the burden and mandate, carrying the burden of the lives of all humans, the burden of faith, struggle and jihad in various places.
- h. Diligent, hardworking and militant (Al-Mubarakfuri 2011, 127).

B. Institution' Image

Image in the big dictionary means appearance, the image that many people have about a person, company, organization or product. According to Philip Kotler (Philip 2002) image is the set of beliefs, ideas and impressions a person holds regarding an object are highly conditioned by that objects's image. Image is also a collection of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a person holds about an object which is strongly conditioned by the image of that object. Image is also the public's perception of a company or its products.

Based on the definition above, image can be interpreted as a picture obtained by the surrounding environment or other parties as a result of their experience and knowledge about an object (madrasa). Therefore, the image of a madrasa institution must be built with a positive value, and the superior programs organized by the madrasa, whether the program is carried out inside or outside the school can support the existence of the image (Suryosubroto 2004, 32).

Images are formed based on a person's experiences with something, so that they can build a mental attitude. And this mental attitude will later be used as a consideration for making decisions because images are considered to represent a person's total knowledge of something. Thus, by making efforts to image the madrasah institution, creating the quality of the madrasah institution, so that the educational process provided at the madrasah is in accordance with the needs of the community and creates satisfaction. Meanwhile, public satisfaction will lead the institution to a better image in the public eyes.

(Walgito 2002, 68), states that stimulus is anything that hits the active receptor which causes the organism to be active. This stimulus can come from within or outside an individual; however, most of the stimulus comes from the outside.

Referring to company theory, customer assessment of a company's image can be measured from four elements, such as: personality, reputation, value, and corporate identity. Some of the indicators are as follows.

- a. Personality is the overall characteristics of a company that is understood by public (trusted, responsible).
- b. Reputation is something was done by a company and believed by the public based on their own experience and other (performance and security).
- c. The values that a company has, or company culture, such as a management attitude that cares about customers, employees who respond quickly to customer requests and complaints.
- d. Company identity is the components that make it easier for the public to recognize the company, such as logos, colors and slogans (Ulum, Arifin, & Fanani 2014, 1–8).

C. Superior Madrasa

Superior Madrasa is madrasah program that was born from the desire to have a madrasah that is able to outstanding at the national and world level, in mastering science, skills and technology supported by good morals. To achieve this excellence, the input, educational processes, teachers and educational staff, management, educational services and supporting facilities must be directed to support the achievement of this goal (Zayadi 2005, 57).

Superior madrasahs need to be supported by professional teaching staff, adequate facilities, innovative curriculum, representative classrooms or learning so they can encourage the creation of effective and efficient learning and produce quality graduates (Bafadal 2006, 86). Furthermore, he explained that not all schools or madrasahs can fulfill these requirements. Technically, the development of superior madrasahs requires professional staff and adequate facilities so that the impact requires quite a lot of learning costs.

The Department of National Education proposed eight criteria to be superior madrasa, namely (1) students who enter are strictly selected and can be accounted for based on academic achievement, psychological and physical tests; (2) educational facilities and infrastructure are met and conducive to the learning process, (3) the climate and atmosphere are supportive for learning activities, (4) teachers and educational staff have high professionalism and an adequate level of welfare, (5) improvise the curriculum to meet the needs of students who generally have high learning motivation compared to their age, (6) student study hours are generally longer due to curriculum demands and student learning needs, (7) the learning process is higher quality and can be accounted for by students and their guardians, and (8) superior schools are beneficial for the environment (Depdikbud 1994).

III. RESULTS

A. Leadership Type of Madrasa Head in Realizing The Institution Image As a Superior Madrasa at MTs Al Hikam Jombang

1. The leader types used at MTs Al Hikam Jombang is combination of various types of leadership, such as:

- a) Visionary leadership which is shown by a vision that goes beyond conditions.
- b) Democratic leadership that shows a willingness to accept the existence of a team.
- c) Innovator leadership or lots of innovation.
- d) Conservator leadership means maintaining organizational integrity by ignoring gaps
- e) Advocate leadership or provider of brilliant solutions.
- f) Administrative leadership shown by emphasizing the madrasa community to always refer to the madrasah vision and mission.
- g) Semi-militaristic leadership within certain limits which is shown by the character of being hardworking, ambitious (if she has a program then she tried hard to succeed), and demanding perfection.
- h) Paternalistic/materialistic, it is motherly leadership type.

2. Behavior type of madrasa head in realizing the institution image as a superior madrasa at MTs Al Hikam Jombang were:

- a) Leadership behavior related to task is: a) prioritize perfection; b) appreciation for achievements and; c) speed in handling problems with a personal and deliberative approach; d) handling subordinates' mistakes with a family approach.
- b) Relation to the pattern of relationship between the leader and subordinates: a) instilling a sense of self-confidence to achieve excellence by implementing all programs perfectly; b) instilling and express high enthusiasm, optimism and belief in becoming a superior madrasa; c) emphasizing collaboration and collectivity with an emphasis on madrasas as shared ownership and responsibility; d) empowering subordinates and supporting subordinates' potential for achievement; e) willing to recognize subordinates' achievements and place achievements as shared success; f) developing family communication patterns.
- c) Relation to the subordinate maturity: a) improving subordinates' abilities through the transfer of knowledge and experience; b) giving authority and responsibility to subordinates by always providing assistance; c) helping resolve problems faced by subordinates while carrying out program duties and responsibilities; d) personally performing actions that exceed the capabilities of subordinates.

3. Tactic type of madrasa head in realizing the institution image as a superior madrasa at MTs Al Hikam Jombang are:

- a) Inviting and influencing the team to work hard, encourage, accompany and fulfill the team's needs at work.
- b) Looking for inspiration and knowledge from outside to be taught towards subordinates and implemented in madrasa.
- c) Developing superior institutional programs including; a) language skills (Arabic and English); b) information technology (ICT); c) organizational skills in the form of OSIS; d) tahfiz Al-Qur'an; e) Adiwiyata madrasa; f) learning yellow book; g) developing various extracurricular programs for theater, wushu, silat, dance, scouts, and so on; h) psychology and career counseling; i) Curriculum of the Ministry of Religion, Ministry of Education and Culture, and the superior of Madrasa Al-Hikam; j) educational tourism (outbound).
- d) Developing social programs or making direct contact with the environment and society a) charity movement program for used plastic bottle waste; b) periodic social action programs for river practice movements in several rivers around the madrasa; c) program for distributing used plastic bottle waste baskets to office institutions and madrasas; d) a movement program to share wall paint resulting from the company's CSR; e) charity movement program for used cooking waste to be made into soap; f) Adiwiyata madrasa mentoring program.
- e) Developing treatment of madrasa human resources in the form of a) using a family approach in establishing communication and solving problems; b) viewing subordinates from their strengths; c) closing the ranks and build understanding; d) setting an example by sending children to their own institutions; e) emphasizing loyalty to madrasas; f) building student achievement; g) publishing through social media on personal and madrasas' accounts; h) providing maximum service; i) instilling a spirit of competition and the belief that Student achievement depends on teacher achievement; j) emphasizing that a good school is when the input is ordinary but the output is extraordinary.

B. Leadership of Madrasa Head in Realizing the Institution's Image as Superior Madrasah at MTsN 16 Jombang

1. The leadership types used at MTsN 16 Jombang is combination of various types of leadership, such as:

- a) Visionary leadership type that displayed high hopes beyond conditions.

- b) Democratic leadership type which showed willingness to accept the existence of personnel who have commitment and responsibility and leave the personnel who did not have commitment and responsibility.
- c) Innovator leadership.
- d) Conservative leadership or maintaining organizational integrity by allowing or eliminating personnel who did not want to work.
- e) Advocate leadership or provider of brilliant solutions to madrasa problems.
- f) Administrative leadership demonstrated by emphasizing madrasa residents to always refer to the madrasah's vision, mission and responsibilities.
- g) Semi-militaristic leadership within certain limits which is shown by the character of being hardworking, ambitious, and demanding perfection.

2. Behavior Type of Madrasa Head in Realizing The Institution Image as Superior Madrasa at MTsN 16 Jombang are:

- a) Such behavior type related to task as: a) prioritizing perfection; b) upholding commitments; c) recognition of performance as achievements and collective property; d) responding to subordinates' mistakes using a reprimand, memorandum and not re-involving them in the program.
- b) Related to subordinates relation are: a) instilling confidence to achieve excellence by implementing all programs perfectly; b) instilling and expressing high enthusiasm, optimism and belief to be superior madrasa; c) commitment to tasks and responsibilities; d) be an inspiring role model; e) placing achievements as mutual success; f) developing report transparency.
- c) Relation to the subordinate maturity: a) improving subordinates' abilities through the transfer of knowledge and experience; b) giving authority and responsibility to subordinates who have the will and commitment on the other hand; c) assisting to overcome the problems faced by subordinates in carrying out their tasks and responsibilities; d) performing actions that exceed the capabilities of subordinates.

3. Tactic Type of Madrasa Head in Realizing the Institutions' Image as Superior Madrasa at MTsN 16 Jombang were:

- a) Discipline, commitment, strong willing, perfection and only involving people who are willing to work.
- b) Development of institutional academic programs in the form of a) English language tutorial in collaboration with EEC; b) Learning al Qur'an and

artil; c) learning yellow book using amtsilati method for grades 7-9 specifically for superior students; d) the tahfiz program is given outside of the school hours (mandatory for superior students at certain times); e) superior class; f) national level environmental schools; g) pioneering child-friendly schools; h) hostel; i) mentoring for students with potential in the field of science (Olympics) for those who have scientific abilities. Development of social programs in the form of a) collaborating with community health centers to become healthy communities; b) collaborating with environmental services to become a clean madrasa; c) Becoming a national Adiwiyata madrasa; d) guiding other schools towards Adiwiyata; e) publication through social media; f) qualify of school health, canteen and library to achieve the good title.

C. Leadership Type of Madrasa Head in Realizing the Institution's Image as Superior Madrasa at MTs Al Hikam and MTsN 16 Jombang

A combination of various leadership types, namely

- a) the visionary leadership type which is shown by a vision that goes beyond the conditions; b) a type of democratic leadership that shows a willingness to accept the existence of all subordinates or limited to personnel who have commitment and responsibility and the death of personnel who do not have commitment and responsibility; c) innovator leadership type (lots of innovation); d) conservator leadership type (maintaining the integrity of the organization) by ignoring gaps or 'allowing' to eliminate personnel who do not want to work; e) advocate leadership type (provider of brilliant solutions); f) the type of administrative leadership shown by emphasizing the madrasa community to always refer to the madrasa vision and mission; and g) a semi-militaristic type of leadership within certain limits which is shown by the character of being hardworking, ambitious (try hard to succeed), and demanding perfection; h) paternalistic/materialistic (motherly) leadership type.

The behavior type of madrasa head in realizing the institution Image as superior madrasa at MTs Al Hikam and MTsN 16 Jombang are: a) leadership behavior in relation to tasks a) prioritizing perfection; b) awards for achievements; c) upholding commitments; d) speed in handling problems with a personal and deliberative approach; e) responding to subordinates' mistakes using family approach, warnings, memorandum and even dismissal.

The leadership behavior of the madrasa head related to the relationship between leader and subordinates, including a) instilling a sense of self-confidence to achieve excellence by implementing all programs perfectly; b) instilling and express high enthusiasm, optimism and belief to be a superior madrasa; c) emphasizing collaboration and collectivity with an emphasis on madrasas as public ownership and responsibility; d) empowering subordinates and supporting

subordinates' potential for achievement; e) willing to recognize subordinates' achievements and place achievements as mutual success; f) developing family communication patterns; g) commitment to tasks and responsibilities; h) inspiring role model; i) developing report transparency.

The leadership behavior of the madrasa head in relation to the maturity of his subordinates: a) improving the abilities of his subordinates through the transfer of knowledge and experience; b) giving authority and responsibility to subordinates by providing assistance to subordinates who have the will and commitment and the other hand; c) helping them to solve problems faced by subordinates while carrying out program tasks and responsibilities; d) performing actions that exceed the capabilities of subordinates.

The tactic type of madrasa head in realizing the institutions' image as superior madrasa at MTs Al Hikam and MTsN 16 Jombang

- a. Inviting and influencing the team to work hard, encourage, accompany and fulfill the team's needs at work.
- b. Looking for inspiration and knowledge from outside to be taught towards subordinates and implemented in madrasa.
- c. Discipline, commitment, strong willing, perfection and only involving people who are willing to work.
- d. Developing superior institutional programs including; a) language skills (Arabic and English); b) information technology (ICT); c) organizational skills in the form of OSIS; d) Tahfiz Al-Qur'an; e) Adiwiyata madrasa; f) learning yellow book; g) developing various extracurricular programs h) psychology and career counseling; i) Curriculum of the Ministry of Religion, Ministry of Education and Culture, and the superior of Madrasa; j) educational tourism (outbound); i) superior class; j) pioneering child-friendly schools; k) hostel; l) mentoring for children with potential in the field of science (Olympics) for children who have scientific abilities.
- e. Developing social programs or have direct contact with the environment and society a) charity movement program for used plastic bottle waste; b) periodic social action programs for river practice movements in several rivers around madrasa; c) program for distributing used plastic bottle waste baskets to office institutions and madrasas; d) a movement program to share wall paint resulting from the company's CSR; e) movement program for alms used cooking waste to be made into soap; f) Adiwiyata madrasa mentoring program; f) collaborate with community health centers to become Healthy madrasa; g) Cooperate with environmental services to become clean madrasa; h) becoming national Adiwiyata madrasa; i) guiding

other schools towards Adiwiyata; j) publication through social media; k) qualify the school health, canteen and library to achieve the good title.

- f. Developing of treatment towards madrasa human source in the form of: a) using family approach to communicate and problem solving; b) assuming subordinates from their strengths; c) closing the ranks and build understanding; d) setting an example by sending children to their own institutions; e) emphasizing loyalty to madrasas; f) building student achievement; g) publishing through social media on personal and madrasas' accounts; h) providing maximum service; i) instilling a spirit of competition and the belief that Student achievement depends on teacher achievement; j) emphasizing that a good school is when the input is ordinary but the output is extraordinary.

IV. DISCUSSION

Leadership type is the leader's way of influencing their subordinates. The research findings found that the type of leadership of madrasa head in realizing the institution image as a superior madrasa is a combination of various types of leadership, such as a) the visionary leadership type displayed with vision that goes beyond its conditions; b) democratic leadership that shows a willingness to accept the existence of all subordinates or personnel who have commitment and responsibility and leave those who do not have commitment and responsibility; c) innovator leadership type (lots of innovation); d) conservative leadership (maintaining organizational integrity) by ignoring gaps or 'allowing' to eliminate personnel who do not want to work; e) advocate leadership (provider of brilliant solutions); f) administrative leadership shown by emphasizing the madrasa community to always refer to madrasa vision and mission; and g) a semi-militaristic type which is shown by the character of being hardworking, ambitious (willing to succeed), and demanding perfection; h) paternalistic (motherly) leadership type.

All of the findings regarding this type of leadership support Hidayat's theory that in carrying out leadership, madrasa heads do not have to implement one type of leadership, but they can implement various types of leadership models, because basically all types of leadership have their respective advantages and weaknesses.

The visionary leadership type was demonstrated by the madrasa heads from two research object (MTs Al Hikam and MTsN 16 Jombang). Both of them emphasized to madrasah residents to instill the vision and mission in their souls. The head of MTs Al Hikam even used composing a song tactic about the madrasa mission. Meanwhile, the head of MTsN 16 Jombang has revised the madrasah's vision and mission to support the goals to be achieved. Hidayat emphasized that visionary leadership is a type of leadership that gives meaning to work together by all components of the

organization by providing direction based on a clearly created vision (Hidayat 2012, 84).

Referring to various research data found, the two madrasa heads can be said as visionary figures, characterized by an attitude accustomed to being proactive, starting with the end in mind, and accustomed to putting the main things first, renewing oneself continuously/self-renewal (Coverly 1989, 168). This type in Kouzes & Posner's concept is described as inspiring a shared vision with the act of seeing the future by imagining thrilling lofty opportunities and gathering people into a shared vision by regarding shared aspirations (Kouzes & Posner 2002, 14)

The democratic leadership type is defined as leadership that opens up active participation from each group, respects the potential of each individual, listens to advice and suggestions from subordinates, and willing to recognize the expertise of specialists in their respective fields, able to utilize the capacity of each member effectively at the right times and conditions. The research findings showed that the type of democratic leadership applied by the head of MTs Al Hikam was slightly different from the head of MTsN 16 Jombang. The head of MTs Al Hikam has the openness to accept the existence of all subordinates without exception, while the head of MTsN 16 Jombang is selective by involving subordinates who have high commitment and responsibility only and ignores or even expel subordinates who do not want to work. This type of democratic leadership in Kouzes & Posner's concept is described as enabling others to act by fostering collaboration and promoting common goals, building trust and strengthening others by sharing power and freedom (Kouzes & Posner 2002, 22).

The innovator leadership type is a leader who innovates a lot (Zichy 2001). The innovator leadership type was demonstrated by the two madrasah heads by carrying out many innovations, especially in relation to the excellence of the madrasa. The characteristics of innovation carried out by the two madrasa heads are almost the same, it started from 'learning' outside the institution and modified to the development madrasah. The action of the madrasa head who is doing a lot of innovation is something must be done because one of the roles of madrasa head is as an innovator/educator, manager, administrator, supervisor, inovator, dan motivator (Mulyasa 2005, 97–98).

(Zichy 2001) explains the leadership's types are; conservator is the leader type who strives hard to maintain the integrity of the organization; innovator is leader types who conduct a lot of innovation. The type of conservator developed by the head of MTs Al Hikam and MTsN 16 is different. The head of MTs Al Hikam regularly reminds her about unity and the need to avoid gaps between madrasa residents as an effort to maintain the organization integrity. Meanwhile, the head of MTsN 16 Jombang chose to eliminate individuals who did not have commitment and willing to work from the program. The next is advocator; it is leadership type who provides brilliant solution. This type is

demonstrated by the two madrasa heads in the form of actions to provide solutions and even as decision maker when there are problems.

The type of administrative leadership is leadership that is able to carry out administrative tasks effectively (Kartono, 2017: 34). The ability of the two madrasa heads to carry out administrative tasks effectively in this research is shown by the ability of the madrasa heads to develop various programs oriented towards realizing the institution image as superior madrasa which will be discussed in the findings regarding leadership tactics.

According to (Kartono 2008, 72) a semi-militaristic type of leadership is shown by the character of being hardworking, ambitious (must be succeed by hard working), and demanding perfection. This type in the context of the head of MTsN 16 Jombang is reflected from the madrasa head's commitment to discipline and her demands for the commitment of his subordinates. Meanwhile, the leadership type is paternalistic/materialistic (motherly) basically examines the natural characteristics inherent towards leaders according to their gender.

Although the charismatic leadership type is not included in the research findings, the figures of the two madrasa heads reflect the presence of a charismatic side. The head of MTs Al Hikam is the madrasa founder daughter and head of the madrasa since it was founded until the time this research was conducted. Meanwhile, the head of MTsN 16 Jombang outside the institution is one of the caretakers of the Tambakberas Jombang Islamic Boarding School. Practically, these two madrasa heads have the charisma of being descendants of *kiai*, Islamic boarding school managers and also heads of formal educational institutions.

The research finding of leadership type in realizing institution image as superior madrasa has supported Zichy theory about eight leadership types was implemented by women leaders, such as trustees (believeness) type, conservators (maintaining), tactician (prioritizing tactic), realistic (prioritizing realistic), strategic (prioritizing rational steps to control situation), innovator (featuring innovation to solve problems), mentor (emphasizing on the motivation given to its followers), advocator (focusing on effort to motivate followers with brilliant ideas or instructions (Zichy 2001).

The finding is also support Tilaar theory about five types of leadership of an Indonesian female leader, namely a) rose type (the type of leader who has great self-confidence); b) orchid type, leader type who is very tenacious, intensive, diligent, tenacious and active in facing various challenges; c) jasmine type, is the leader type who is simple, self-effacing, very honest and wise; d) lotus type, that is the type of leader who is honest and independent; e) cempaka type, or the leader type who is full of responsibility, nurturing and provides a role model (Tilaar & Widarto 2003).

A. The Leadership Behavior of Madrasa Heads in Realizing the Institution's Image to Become Superior Madrasa

The leadership behavior of madrasa heads in this study refers to three dimensions of leadership behavior proposed by Mulyasa, namely: a) task behavior which refers to giving instructions to subordinates including certain explanations, (something must be done, time, and the way to do, and monitor them closely; b) relationship behavior refers to how invitations are conveyed through two-way communication which includes listening and involving subordinates in problem solving; c) maturity refers to the ability and willingness of subordinates to be responsible for carrying out the tasks assigned to them (Efendi 2015, 158–59).

The research findings showed that the leadership behavior of madrasa heads in realizing the institution image as a superior madrasa is as follows:

- 1) Leadership behavior of tasks: a) prioritizing perfection; b) awards for achievements; c) upholding commitments; d) speed in handling problems with a personal and deliberative approach; e) responding to subordinates' mistakes with a family approach, warnings, memorandum and even dismissal.

Regarding leadership behavior of tasks, Bass & Avolio as quoted by Sahertian stated that there are three indicators, namely a) contingent reward is behavior that recognizes employee achievements and explains expectations; b) management by-exception-active is the behavior of a leader who will take immediate action to correct problems and point out errors occurred; and c) management by exception-passive is the leader behavior who will wait until the problem becomes chronic or serious before making corrections (Sahertian & Matahero 2010).

Referring to the research findings and indicators proposed, the researcher emphasized that the leadership role of the madrasa head in realizing the institution image related to tasks is an accumulation of contingent reward and management by-exception-active indicators. The attitudes and behavior of the two madrasa heads in this study did not take any action at all that reflected the behavior of letting the problem drag on (management by exception-passive).

- 2) The leadership behavior of the madrasa head related to the relationship between the leader and his subordinates: a) instilling a sense of self-confidence to achieve excellence by implementing all programs perfectly; b) instilling and express high enthusiasm, optimism and belief to be superior madrasa; c) emphasizing collaboration and collectivity with an emphasis on madrasas as public ownership and responsibility; d) empowering subordinates and supporting subordinates' potential for achievement; e) willing to recognize subordinates' achievements and place achievements as shared success; f) develop family communication

patterns; g) commitment to tasks and responsibilities; h) inspiring role model; i) developing report transparency.

Regarding leadership behavior related to the relationship between leaders and subordinates, Sahertian, stated that there are five indicators, namely a) idealized influence/attributed; b) idealized influences/behaviors, c) inspirational motivation, d) intellectual stimulation, and e) individualized considerations (Sahertian & Matahero 2010). In this case, these five indicators can be found in the leadership behavior of the two madrasa heads in realizing the institution image as a superior madrasa which is the subject of research.

- 3) The leadership behavior of the madrasa head in relation to the maturity of his subordinates a) always improves the abilities of his subordinates through the transfer of knowledge and experience; b) giving authority and responsibility to subordinates by providing assistance to subordinates who have the will and commitment on the other hand; c) helping them to solve the problems faced by subordinates while carrying out program tasks and responsibilities; d) performing actions that exceed the subordinates capabilities.

This study of leadership behavior in relation to the maturity level of subordinates refers to Blanchard's theory. He suggested that there are five indicators to measure leadership behavior related to the maturity of subordinates, namely; a) informing/telling (high assignment, low relationship); b) peddling/selling (high assignment, high relationship) c) involving/participating (low assignment, high relationship); d) delegating or low assignment, low relationship (Blanchard & Hersey 2013, 80).

B. Tactics of Women Leaders in Realizing the Institution's Image to Become Superior Madrasa

The research findings showed that the madrasa head's leadership tactics in realizing the institution image as a superior madrasa are: 1) inviting and influencing the team to work hard, encourage, accompany and fulfill the team's needs in their work; 2) looking for inspiration and knowledge from outside to be taught to subordinates and implemented in madrasas; 3) having discipline, commitment, strong will, perfection and involving people who are willing to work only; 4) developing superior institutional programs including a) language skills (Arabic and English); b) information technology (ICT); c) Organization skills in the form of OSIS; d) tahfiz Al-Qur'an; e) Adiwiyata Madrasa; f) learning yellow book; g) developing various extracurricular programs; h) counseling guidance of psychology and careers; i) curriculum of the Ministry of Religion, Education and Culture, and leading madrasa; j) educational tourism (outbound); i) superior class; j) pioneering child-friendly schools; k) hostel; l) mentoring for children with potential Olympics) for those who have scientific abilities; 5) developing social programs or having direct contact with the environment and society; a) using plastic bottle waste charity movement program; b)

periodic social action programs for river practice movements in several rivers around the madrasa; c) program for distributing used plastic bottle waste baskets to office institutions and madrasas; d) a movement program to share wall paint resulting from the company's CSR; e) movement program for alms used cooking waste to be made into soap; f) Adiwiyata madrasa mentoring program; g) collaborate with community health centers; h) collaborate with environmental services to become a clean madrasa; i) becoming a national Adiwiyata madrasa; j) guiding other schools towards Adiwiyata; k) publication through social media; l) qualify the school health, canteen and library to achieve the good title; m) developing treatment of madrasa human resources in the form of; a) a family approach in establishing communication and solving problems; b) viewing subordinates in terms of their strengths; c) closing ranks and build understanding; d) setting an example by sending students to their own institutions; e) emphasizing loyalty to madrasa; f) building student achievement; g) publishing through social media on personal and madrasa accounts; h) providing maximum service; i) instilling a spirit of competition and the belief that The students success depends on the success of teacher; j) emphasizing that a good school is when the input is ordinary and the output is extraordinary.

The tactics developed by the two madrasa heads in realizing the image of the institution as a superior madrasa are in line with the Bafadhah concept under superior madrasahs born from the desire to have a madrasa that is capable of achieving the national level (Bafadhah 2006, 86). The two madrasahs started as ordinary madrasahs and were unable to compete, but with the strong desire of the madrasah head, the two madrasahs won several national level awards.

The research findings also strengthen Suryaboroto's opinion that to build and maintain the image of a madrasa as a superior madrasa, it cannot be separated from the existence of superior programs organized by the madrasah, whether the program is carried out inside or outside the school (Suryosubroto 2004, 32). Referring to the results of the discussion of the research findings above, the following proposition can be formulated.

V. CONCLUSION

The type, behavior, and tactic of madrasa head in realizing the institution' image as a superior madrasa at MTs Al Hikam Jombang and MTsN 16 Jombang are:

1. The leadership type both of them was combination of various types of leadership, especially the visionary, democratic, innovator, conservator, and advocate, administrative, semi-militaristic and charismatic types.
2. The leadership behavior of them was pattern of leadership actions in relation to tasks, relationships with subordinates and the level of maturity of subordinates between leaders and tasks, subordinates and the level of maturity of

subordinates which reflects the existence of contingent reward, management by-exception-active, idealized influence/attributed, idealized influence/behaviors, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, telling, selling, participating, and delegating.

3. The leadership tactics of them were using the approach of will, discipline, commitment, self-confidence, development of superior academic and extracurricular programs, development of social and environmental programs as well as monitoring institutions, teachers and students to be outstanding.

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